

1. Introduction

Currently (2021), solid mineral resources are mined in 178 countries around the world. The mineral resources extracted from the earth's interior form the basis for the existence of a technocratic civilization. The main mining methods for open-pit mining of solid mineral resources are:

- 1) destruction of parts of a rock body;
- 2) loading of the rock body into suitable vehicles;
- 3) transportation of the rock body from the place of its formation in the quarries to the areas of the Earth's surface located near the planning contours of the quarries, using various traditional methods.

The technical and economic analysis of the technological process of transporting rock masses in the operated quarries using traditional means of transport, e.g. motor vehicles, conveyor belts, etc., operated by lifting machines, has shown that the cost of transporting 1 ton of rock masses is considerable and the productivity of personnel is extremely low. For example, at a pit depth of 600 m, the volume of overburden removed from the design contour of the pit during construction of a haulage berm in the pit is large and exceeds 150 million m³. If parts of the overburden are removed above the transport berm, the volume is about 100 million m³, and the financial cost is 2.5 to 3.0 billion USD [1]. One of the modern and sustainable trends and patterns in the field of open pit mining is the creation of automated dispatch systems for mining vehicles. However, the known systems [2] for solid mineral development in open pit mining use conventional machines for transportation of rock mass, which does not reduce the cost of transportation of 1 ton of rock mass.

In this context, the development of an expert system for automating the disposition of mining transport machines with a subsystem for selecting and justifying the innovative appearance of a machine for transporting rock masses with the control of operating parameters taking into account the stochastic conditions of the mined sections of the rock mass is an urgent task. The obtained results should be used in the operation of quarries with unlimited annual productivity, e.g. up to 300 million tons of rock mass or more, and unlimited depth, e.g. up to 3000 m or more, ensuring the effective values of technical and economic in-

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGY TO SOLVE THE PROBLEMS OF AUTOMATION OF MINING AND GEOLOGICAL WORKS

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Abstract: The object of research relates to the field of control systems for mining and transportation machinery in the development of solid mineral deposits in open-cut mining. The problem of reducing the cost of transporting 1 ton of rock mass and increasing the efficiency of these machines is solved. The article develops an expert system for the disposition of mining vehicles with a subsystem for the selection of their innovative appearance with the ability to control their operating parameters, taking into account the stochastic conditions of the developed sections of the rock. The mathematical model for the construction of the future appearance of a mining and transportation machine, based on its functional and economic evaluation, reduces to the solution of the problem of optimization of the generalized criterion of required efficiency. As an example of private indicators of their effectiveness in operation, there is an expert analysis of the evaluation of options for solutions, for example, structural-kinematic and operational parameters of these machines, etc. Innovative designs of a trough body of any size of the carrying capacity of single-rope and multi-rope steep elevators for highly profitable mining in quarries are justified unlimited values of their depth and annual productivity. In the proposed study, the values of the resistance forces to the destruction of a section of a rock mass, determined by analytical and experimental methods, are refined by finding the optimal Kalman coefficient, which increases the efficiency of the use of mining and transport machines. The proposed methods allow the development of innovative mining and transport machines with the ability to control their operating parameters taking into account the stochastic conditions of the mined rock section.

Keywords: open pit mining, dispatching system, rock mass, skip hoist, counterweight.

dicators of fossil mining, i.e. high profitability, ensuring safe working conditions for personnel and excluding harmful effects on the environment during use and operation in all climatic conditions.

2. Methods

The studies were carried out on the basis of the theory and practice of mining solid mineral deposits in quarries, including the analysis of the technological process of transporting rock masses from quarries. The selection of mining and transport vehicles, e.g. the use of excavators at planned extraction sites in a quarry, was investigated. The technical and economic analysis of the technological process of transporting rock masses in operated quarries using road transport, conveyor belts, and transporting rock masses using single-rope and multi-rope inclined elevators operated by hoisting machines showed that it is unprofitable to use a conventional way of transporting rock masses in quarries with a depth of 600 m or more. The studies were conducted using the methodology of a systematic approach to analysis and synthesis in the analysis of complex business processes of the systems of modern enterprises, which include the technological process of development of deposits of solid minerals in a quarry. The systems of management of quality indicators of ore flow in open pit mining were studied, using various geographic information systems, such as the Global Positioning System, as well as systems of simulation of business processes of modern enterprises. It was found that in the existing information systems for disposition of mining and transportation machines there

are no subsystems for selection of their innovative appearance with control of their operating parameters taking into account stochastic conditions of the destroyed section of the rock mass. Rational designs of innovative single-rope and multi-rope inclined hoists for transportation of rock masses in a quarry were prepared. Based on the functional-economic approach, innovative designs of the trough body of any size of its carrying capacity of single-rope and multi-rope inclined elevators for highly profitable, environmentally friendly mining in quarries with unlimited depth and annual productivity are justified.

The study was conducted using the methods of machine and mechanism theory, as well as methods of mathematical

modeling, such as probabilistic and uncertain mathematical models for optimal management decisions. On this basis, a mathematical model was developed and created to construct the perspective appearance of mining and transportation machinery and its functional and structural evaluation, reduced to the solution of a multi-criteria problem based on one of the following methodological principles: Convolution of a system of individual criteria into a generalized criterion of desired effect (efficiency); determination of the main criterion and constraints on other indicators.

The study was conducted using the methods of machine and mechanism theory, as well as the methods of mathematical modeling, such as probabilistic and uncertain mathematical models for optimal management decisions. On this basis, a mathematical model for the construction of a perspective view of mining and transport vehicles was developed and created using the example of a bulldozer and its functional and structural evaluation, which was reduced to the solution of a multi-criteria problem according to one of the following methodological principles: Folding a system of sub-criteria into a generalized criterion of desired effect (efficiency); defining the main criterion and constraints for other indicators. Methods of justification and selection of structural, dimensional and operational parameters of the adaptive actuator of a bulldozer cutter with removable cutting shield were developed, taking into account the principle of adaptation to the conditions of the mined section of the rock massif. These methods form the basis for the development of innovative and competitive adaptive actuators for the working bodies of mining and transport machines. The research methodology is based on a systematic approach in which the execution mechanism of the bulldozer – the environment to be developed – is considered as a single system of interconnected and interacting elements.

3. Results

In the process of developing and creating a mathematical model for constructing a promising appearance of mining and transport machines, their functional and structural assessment is reduced to solving the problem: folding a system of particular criteria into a generalized criterion of the required effect (efficiency).

These criteria characterize a mining and transport machine that has the following operational parameters: productivity, reliability, adaptability to the conditions of the technological process, productivity, equipment with replaceable working bodies, control system, infrastructure and comprehensive provision of spare parts [3].

The implementation of the algorithm for selecting many criteria consists in constructing a generalized criterion by linear convolution of the criteria. It boils down to the fact that the generalized criterion is expressed as a linear combination of the values of the remaining criteria:

$$U(x)=\sum w_i x_i, \tag{1}$$

where w_i is the weight (importance) of the i -th criterion assigned by experts;

x_i is the quantitative assessment according to the X_i -th criterion.

The structure of the appearance of the skip hoist is changing due to ongoing activities aimed at increasing the value of one or another of its parameters. The solution of the problem comes down to rebuilding the structure of the state of the appearance of the skip hoist, trying to bring it closer to the final, target state.

The economic part of the calculation block of the presented methodology begins with determining the need for financial resources to implement the plan for the formation of a new look for the skip hoist in full and the time required to achieve this goal with a given level of funding, which are determined by the formula:

$$\Phi=\sum(K_i-C_i)\cdot S_i, \tag{2}$$

where Φ is the need for additional financial resources for the implementation of the program for the formation of a new look for the skip hoist at a given level of funding; K_i is the value of the i -th parameter of the prospective appearance of the skip hoist; C_i is the value of the i -th parameter of the existing shape of the skip hoist; S_i is the price per unit of the i -th measure of the formation of a new look for the skip hoist.

Term T , during which the program for the formation of a new look of the skip hoist will be implemented, is determined by the formula:

$$T=\Phi/F, \tag{3}$$

where T is the period during which the program for the formation of a new image of the skip hoist will be implemented; F is the need for additional financial resources for the implementation of the program for the formation of a promising image of the skip hoist at a given level of funding.

After that, the rate of deviation of the initial state of the existing shape of the skip hoist from its final target state is calculated, expressed as a percentage, which is determined by the formula:

$$N=(\sum C_i/K_i)/I, \tag{4}$$

where N is the norm of the existing state of the appearance of the skip hoist; I is the total number of parameters characterizing the structure of the existing appearance of the skip hoist [3].

The final solution of the problem comes down to finding the maximum value of the norm of deviation of the achieved parameters of the state of the prospective appearance of the skip hoist for a given level of funding:

$$H \rightarrow \max; \\ H=(\sum P_i/K_i)/I, \tag{5}$$

and

$$F=\sum(P_i-C_i)\cdot S_i, \tag{6}$$

where H is the norm of the achieved state of the prospective appearance of the skip hoist; P_i is the value of the i -th parameter of the achieved perspective appearance of the skip hoist; S_i is the price per unit of the i -th measure of the formation of the prospective image of the skip hoist; F is a given level of (allocated) funding for the formation of a perspective image of a skip hoist within a certain period of time (usually within one year); K_i – the value of the i -th parameter of the final, target perspective appearance of the skip hoist; C_i is the value of the i -th parameter of the existing shape of the skip hoist; i is the serial number of the structure parameter of the existing shape of the skip hoist [3].

The results of calculating the parameters of the functional-economic model for assessing the prospective appearance of the skip hoist during a given period of time, performed for a conditional example, are shown in **Table 1**.

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Table 1
Initial data and calculation results of the perspective view of the skip hoist for a conditional example

The Appearance of the skip hoist					
Allocated funds, unit, 70	Required funds, unit, 144	Time to achieve the goal, year, 2.5	Initial state norm %, 64	The rate of the achieved state, %, 81	
Calculation results					
Parameter name	The initial state	Required Appearance	Unit price	Received appearance, %	Perspective appearance (goal achievement), %
Safe working conditions for quarry personnel	38	50	2	80	100
Reduced downtime of the skip hoist by taking into account the stochastic conditions of the developed area of the rock mass	16	20	2	80	100
The carrying capacity of the skip body can be different, for example, from 50 tons to 100 thousand tons of rock mass and more	4	10	2	100	100
Low energy consumption when transporting the rock mass with an innovative skip hoist with a counterweight	16	20	5	80	100
Reliability of structural components and parts of the innovative skip hoist and the simplicity of its control system	8	10	5	80	80
Improving the ecology inside the quarry	7	15	5	80	100
Low production cost of skip hoist	3	4	10	80	100
Low maintenance cost of skip hoist	1	3	10	80	100

In the second stage, the calculation is detailed, determining the achieved calculated indicators in relation to the final target parameter of the state of perspective appearance of the skip. **Table 1** shows the deviations of each calculated indicator in relation to the final perspective appearance of the skip loader. The structure of the achieved perspective appearance of the skip has changed significantly, the value of a parameter (in the conditional example it has the number 3), which is 4 % above the initial state, has reached 100 % [3].

4. Discussion

Functional and economic evaluation of rock mining using traditional mining haulage machinery proposed in the article, e.g., motor vehicles, conveyor belts, single-rope and multi-rope inclined hoists operated by haulage machinery, has shown that rock mining in quarries with depths of 600 m and more is unprofitable. The development of a mathematical model for the construction of a prospective appearance of mining and transport machines on the basis of their functional and structural evaluation reduces to the solution of the problem: convolution of a system of partial criteria into a generalized criterion of desired effect (efficiency). These criteria characterize a mining and transport machine that has the following operational parameters: productivity, reliability, adaptability to the conditions of the technological process, efficiency, equipment with interchangeable working bodies, control system, infrastructure and comprehensive spare parts supply, etc. The results of the calculation of the parameters of the functional and economic model for evaluating the appearance of the skip loader during a certain period of time, which was carried out for a conditional example, are presented in **Table 1**.

Based on the developed functional-economic approach [4, 5], this paper proposes a promising view for a skip loader for transporting rock masses in a quarry. Several variants of innovative single-rope and multi-rope skip loaders without a hoisting machine are proposed, the use of which allows transporting lumpy rock masses in one step in a skip loaders with unlimited volume, e.g. up to 100 thousand tons and more, in quarries with unlimited depth, e.g. up to 3000 m and more, at annual productivity of a quarry up to 300 million tons of aggregates and more, excluding harmful effects of the technological process of transportation of aggregates on the environment and during its operation in all climatic conditions[6].

Methods have been developed for substantiating and selecting the structural, dimensional and regime parameters of the operating mechanism of the working body of a mining transport machine using the example of a bulldozer blade with a removable cutting knife, taking into account the stochastic conditions of the developed section of the rock mass [7–9], which increases the accuracy of their assessment. These methods are the basis for creating innovative competitive adaptive actuators of the working bodies of mining and transport machines. In [10], the soil conditions for the operation of earth-moving machines in Kazakhstan were studied. Experimental results of studies of the process of destruction of soils and rocks are presented. At the same time, it is noted that one of the main factors affecting the efficiency of the process of destruction of soils and rocks is the angle of destruction α_p (cutting angle formed by the path of motion and the leading edge of the cutting wedge). In the same place, the regression dependence of the force of resistance to destruc-

tion of a section of the soil mass (rock mass) on the geometric parameters of the bulldozer blade, the strength coefficient of the destroyed section of the soil mass K_p and the depth of its destruction (cutting) at known intervals of change in the value of the angle of destruction (cutting) α_p . In this study, the analytical dependence between the cutting angle and the structural-kinematic parameters of the bulldozer blade actuator is substantiated (8). This circumstance increases the accuracy of estimating the cutting resistance force of the rock mass and allows to automatically adjust the cutting depth of the rock mass by changing the structural and kinematic parameters of the bulldozer blade actuator. The theoretical provisions set forth in the study were confirmed by experimental studies to establish a confidence interval for estimating the mathematical expectation of a random value of the cutting resistance force of the rock mass (soil category III (clay) in the interval of changing the cutting angle $20^\circ < \alpha_p < 30^\circ$). The value of the average sample of the random value of the cutting resistance force of the III category soil at $n=50$ was $P=81.35$ kN.

5. Conclusions

The results obtained are the theoretical basis for the creation by an expert dispatching system of mining transport machines with a subsystem for selecting their innovative appearance with the ability to control their operational parameters, taking into account the stochastic conditions of the developed sections of the rock mass. This system is intended to be used in the operation of quarries, the annual productivity of which is unlimited, for example, up to 300 million tons of rock

mass or more, and the depth of the quarry is unlimited, for example, up to 3000 m or more, while ensuring effective values of technical and economic indicators of mining fossils, highly profitable, ensuring safe working conditions for personnel, eliminating harmful effects on the environment during their use and operation under any climatic conditions.

In subsequent articles, it is planned to present research on the development and creation of mathematical and computer models of the perspective appearance of a skip hoist for transporting rock mass in a quarry and its main structural elements. It is planned to test the working version of the automated dispatching system for the control and dispatching system of mining transport machines with an expert subsystem for choosing their innovative appearance with the ability to control their operational parameters, taking into account the stochastic conditions of the developed sections of the rock mass in the development of deposits of solid minerals in an open way.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest in relation to this research, whether financial, personal, authorship or otherwise, that could affect the research and its results presented in this paper.

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Data availability

Manuscript has no associated data.

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